

Pedagogical Challenges and Opportunities when Teaching Large Class Cohorts

Proceedings of the PHELC/TEU DCU Seminar
Polaris Building, Glasnevin Campus, Dublin City University

Thursday 4th December, 2025, 10am - 1.30pm

Facilitated by Dr Ann Marie Farrell
and Dr Martina Crehan, DCU

Editors: Ann Marie Farrell, Martina Crehan and Patricia Flanagan

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And finally, to the staff who attended the seminar and those who presented on the day, a sincere thank you. It is so important for higher education colleagues to share practice and learning in relation to pedagogy, especially in the context of large classes which are often perceived and experienced as challenging. Thank you for your generosity.

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Introduction

Welcome to the proceedings of the seminar for staff of Dublin City University entitled ***Pedagogical Challenges and Opportunities when Teaching Large Class Cohorts***. The seminar was held on Thursday, 4th December 2025, 10am - 1.30pm in DCU's newest building, *Polaris*.

Alongside a range of shifts and innovations in pedagogy, the large-group format remains deeply embedded in the higher education landscape. It presents both challenges and opportunities for educators and students alike, and the seminar was designed to highlight examples of practice which positively harnessed the opportunities within the challenges.

Staff from across the university came together to discuss their practice and research in the context of teaching large class cohorts. The seminar was characterised by the enthusiasm and generosity of those presenting, who kindly shared their knowledge, experience and expertise with the attendees. Presenters provided an extended abstract using the Rolfe, Freshwater and Jasper (2001) framework for critical reflection containing the subheadings *What? So What? Now What?*, all of which were peer reviewed, the final versions of which are provided in this set of proceedings. The proceedings illustrate how educators from across various disciplinary areas are designing and reflecting upon teaching in the large class context from the use of technology to the application of specific pedagogical approaches such as challenge based learning. We thank all who contributed and hope that the examples cited provide inspiration for others who wish to innovate in this space.

The seminar was co-hosted by PHELC and DCU's Teaching Enhancement Unit (TEU), and it is the intention of PHELC to host similar institutional based events every two years, while the international PHELC symposium will be held every other year.

We hope that the case studies provided in these proceedings support and/or inspire you in your own pedagogical practice in the large class context.

Ann Marie Farrell
PHELC Convenor

Martina Crehan
TEU, DCU

Agenda for the Day

Pedagogical Challenges and Opportunities when Teaching Large Class Cohorts

PHELC/TEU DCU Seminar

Room FTG09, Polaris Building, Glasnevin Campus

Thursday 4th December, 2025, 10am - 1.30pm

- 9.30 **Tea/Coffee on arrival**
- 10.00 **Official Opening**
Welcome
Overview of Seminar
- 10.20 **SESSION ONE: Assessment in Large Classes**
- Paul Davis, Business School** - Designing authentic and reflective assessment to address AI challenges in a large final-year supply chain management module
- Christina Hannify & Ann Marie Farrell, Institute of Education** - Making Authentic Assessment Work at Scale: Lessons and Limitations - Warts and All.
- Yalemisew Agbaz, Faculty of Engineering and Computing** - Formative assessments co-created with students (FACCTs) for large classes
- Karen Buckley, Institute of Education** - Reimagining feedback at scale: using 'sense checks' to model inclusive pedagogy in a large-class teacher education programme
- 11.20 **SESSION TWO: Teaching Approaches in Large Classes**
- Regina Connolly & Peter Robbins, Business School** - Co-Teaching for Impact: A Team-Led Approach to AI and Sustainable Innovation
- Reihaneh Aghamolaei, Faculty of Engineering and Computing:** Digital transformation for active, inclusive, and sustainable learning in a large engineering module
- Tara Concannon-Gibney, Institute of Education:** Using Self-Study to Enhance the Teaching of Self-Study with Pre-Service Teachers
- 12.10 **Break**
-

12.30

Session Three: Learning and Engagement in Large Classes

Colette Real & Catherine Faherty, Business School - Transforming Business Education: The Impact of the LIFE Module at Dublin City University

Leah Ridgway & Derek Molloy, Faculty of Engineering and Computing: Balancing Efficiency and Effectiveness: Learning in Large Class Electronics Laboratories

Paul Buchanan, Faculty of Science and Health: Supporting Diverse Learners in Large First-Year Classes through Adaptive Digital Tools: Integrating McGraw Hill Connect in Anatomy and Physiology

1.15

Concluding comments

1.30

Lunch

This seminar is followed by a workshop on **Peer Observation** after lunch in the same location. This workshop requires separate registration. Please see relevant emails and/or TEU weekly newsletters for information.

SESSION ONE: ASSESSMENT IN LARGE CLASSES

Designing Authentic and Reflective Assessment to Address AI Challenges in a Large Final-Year Supply Chain Management Module

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Keywords: Supply Chain Management; Assessment Design; Artificial Intelligence; Reflective Practice; Large Class Pedagogy; Andragogy

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What?

This abstract presents a reimagined assessment structure designed to uphold assessment integrity and engagement in a final-year undergraduate Supply Chain Management module with 194 students across 8 programmes. The module is one semester in duration and carries 5 ECTS credits. The module and all assessments are managed and delivered by one member of staff, requiring careful coordination of each stage of the assessment process. All assessments are individual to reduce the risk of collusion and AI-generated content. Drawing on andragogical principles and experiential learning theory, four scaffolded assignments were designed:

1. Historical Essay: A written research task exploring historical supply chains (20%)
2. Current Issue Assessment: A written research task analysing strategic chokepoints in contemporary supply chains (30%)
3. Conceptual Design (3D Model): An applied creative task requiring students to design a circular supply chain and build a 3D model using recyclable materials. The students must also present a 1000 word document and also a video (3 – 5 minutes) explaining their 3D model (45%)
4. Reflective Video: A video final reflective submission (worth 5%) encouraging students to consider what the activity taught them about supply chain systems, creativity, and sustainability

So What?

The growing prevalence of generative artificial intelligence tools poses a substantial challenge to traditional assessment methods, particularly in large-class contexts. In modules where assessment is primarily essay-based, AI-generated content can significantly compromise academic integrity. As Foley and Masingila

(2014) argue, large class pedagogy often suffers from a lack of meaningful interaction and oversight, and this is exacerbated when assessment design does not evolve in line with new digital risks. Hornsby and Osman (2014) similarly warn that massification in higher education has made it harder to ensure authentic learning experiences. In this context, authenticity, creativity, and physical engagement become powerful tools to reclaim assessment as a site of learning rather than a site of surveillance.

To address these challenges, this module explicitly draws on andragogical principles that prioritise active, self-directed, and problem-based learning (Knowles, 1980; Brookfield, 2017). By embedding a scaffolded assessment journey that starts with research-based tasks and builds towards a creative, physical output, culminating in a personal reflection, students are required to engage cognitively, emotionally, and practically with the learning content. This design approach aligns with the principles of backward design (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005), where intended learning outcomes guide the construction of assessments that authentically measure student understanding. The 3D model assignment exemplifies “learning by doing” and echoes Boud, Keogh, and Walker’s (1985) advocacy for learning through reflective engagement with experience.

The final reflective assignment (worth 5%) is designed to encourage metacognitive awareness, asking students to consider how the physical act of constructing a model influenced their understanding of circular supply chains. This links strongly to Brookfield’s (2017) model of critically reflective teaching, which encourages both students and teachers to consider how assumptions, context, and emotion shape learning.

Importantly, the assessment design aligns with the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework (Rose, Gravel, & Gordon, 2014), providing multiple means of expression (e.g., physical models, video presentations, reflective writing). This approach fosters deeper engagement for a diverse cohort, as advocated by Koh (2017) in her work on authentic assessment, which promotes real-world relevance and student autonomy. Further, the emphasis on a physical artefact and oral explanation disrupts AI misuse by requiring personal creativity and context-specific application, both difficult to automate.

However, the approach presents significant challenges. Staff workload implications are substantial: assessing each individual assessment across 194 students, particularly the physical 3D models and video presentations, requires considerable time and effort. Scaffolding the work so that each assessment logically builds from one to the next proved complex, requiring careful sequencing and clear communication of expectations. The diverse range of students spread across eight programmes, involving a mix of Irish and international students, created additional challenges, as not all students were familiar with Irish third-level grading conventions and expectations. This required additional scaffolding and explicit communication about assessment criteria and standards.

In essence, the design of this assessment structure addresses both the pedagogical constraints of large-class teaching (De Rogatis et al., 2014) and the emergent risks posed by AI. It offers a replicable model for other disciplines seeking to maintain engagement, academic integrity, and inclusivity in assessment, while acknowledging the significant resource demands such an approach entails.

Now What?

I am now reviewing the approach taken. So far it seems to have demonstrated increased student engagement, higher-quality submissions, and more original work. Students are reporting enjoying the physical and visual nature of the 3D model. From previous work done over the last three years the reflective piece has added a metacognitive layer to the learning process. Moving forward, this model will be iterated upon with greater use of formative feedback loops and embedded reflection throughout the module. More broadly, this approach offers a viable blueprint for maintaining academic integrity and learner engagement in large class teaching, especially in the face of AI disruption.

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Making Authentic Assessment Work at Scale: Lessons and Limitations - Warts and All

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What?

Authentic assessment engages students in tasks that closely mirror the complex, real-world challenges of their future professional practice, requiring them to apply knowledge and skills in meaningful contexts (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024). Implementing such assessment in large-cohort settings introduces distinctive pedagogical constraints, where the scale of participation can limit opportunities for dialogue, interaction, and personalised support (Cuseo, 2007). In our first-year Bachelor of Education module (~450 students), student teachers collaboratively analysed complex, real-world pedagogical dilemmas drawn from recently qualified teachers' (RQTs) classroom experiences. These dilemmas, centred on inclusion and learner diversity, formed the foundation of an assessment task in which students were required to develop evidence-informed, practical responses to authentic educational challenges. This design aimed to connect theory to practice while enhancing student engagement and emphasising real-life relevance, showing that it is possible for large classes to maintain engagement if teaching and assessment strategies are carefully adapted (De Matos-Ala & Hornsby, 2015). Underpinned by socio-constructivist theory (Wenger, 2002), the approach positioned assessment as both a learning tool and an evaluative framework by engaging students in collaborative meaning-making, requiring them to demonstrate not only what they know but also how they would apply that knowledge to the complex realities of classroom practice (Sokhanvar et al., 2021).

So What?

Translating the ideals of authenticity into practice at scale revealed the complexities of assessment's "double duty": its summative function of judging performance and its formative role in supporting learning (Carless, 2015). Authentic assessment must both measure achievement fairly and promote learning through constructive feedback. Balancing these purposes proved challenging in a large-class context, where scale amplifies well-documented pedagogical constraints (Cuseo, 2007), including reduced opportunities for personalised or dialogic feedback, uneven participation across large groups, and the challenges of supporting first-year students to navigate assessment criteria and rubrics without the level of guidance typically possible in smaller cohorts. Large cohorts also introduce interactional challenges: sustaining meaningful dialogue with and between students, facilitating peer collaboration at scale, and fostering the deeper cognitive engagement often inhibited in large, lecture-dominant environments (Cuseo, 2007).

These spatial constraints required deliberate pedagogical responses, including the use of workshop-style activities to scaffold the assessment task, strategic grouping of students, and careful orchestration to maintain interaction and dialogue. Such strategies were necessary precisely because large classes tend to restrict the types of assignments and learning activities feasible at scale (Cuseo, 2007; De Matos-Ala & Hornsby, 2015). Yet despite these challenges, anecdotal feedback from students indicated high levels of engagement and appreciation for the task's relevance and realism, as well as for the workshop-style, co-facilitated format, which created a more supported and interactive experience within the large-class environment. This suggests that, even within the constraints of large-class teaching, carefully designed authentic tasks can create meaningful learning opportunities and foster a sense of relevance and participation at scale (De Matos-Ala & Hornsby, 2015).

Now What?

Our reflections highlight not only the challenges but also the unintended learning for teaching academics. The process fostered new strategies for managing feedback and assessment logistics, deeper collaboration within the teaching team, and the emergence of a network of RQTs as collaborators in assessment design. The experience also illuminated pedagogical possibilities inherent in large-class contexts, such as leveraging peer-to-peer learning, distributed facilitation, and collaborative problem-solving at scale. Crucially, the experience also prompted us to reconsider how physical learning spaces can better support interaction and engagement in large-class contexts. Moving forward, these insights will inform further refinement of our assessment approaches, feedback processes, and spatial design practices. This presentation offers a candid exploration of what it takes to make authentic assessment work at scale, sharing both the “warts” and the wins.

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Formative Assessments Co-Created with Students (FACcTS) for Large Classes

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Keywords: Formative Assessments, Active Learning, Co-creation, UDL, Metacognition

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What?

This paper reports lessons learned from designing and implementing Formative Assessments Co-Created with Students (FACcTS) in a large-scale Data Literacy and Analytics module (CSC1015) delivered asynchronously to over 2,000 DCU students from 15 programs across five faculties annually since 2022 (Abgaz & Dunne, 2023). CSC1015 is designed using a microcurricula approach covering 14 Data Literacy and Analytics Topics (DLATs) —0.5 to 1 ECTS, each with independent Loop page—that can be composed into 5 ECTS module, and flexibly delivered in Sem I, II, and year-long setting. FACcTS were introduced in response to student feedback indicating the need for additional supports that improve engagement, topic retention, and preparation for summative assessments in an online learning environment (Farrell et al., 2021; Hornsby, 2020). Grounded in active learning (Christersson et al., 2019; Stoerger & Krieger, 2016) and Universal Design for Learning principles (Emmers et al., 2022; Farrell, 2021; Flood & Banks, 2021), the approach leverages interactive digital platforms such as Loop and H5P (Magro, 2021) to implement FACcTS. Students who had previously completed the module collaborated to summarise key topics and convert them into diverse formative assessment items—such as multiple-choice, true/false, drag-and-drop, matching, and fill-in-the-blank questions—using H5P’s interactive features. FACcTS, by design, embedded detailed immediate feedback for each question leading students to the content of the specific sub-topic covered in the questions (Broadbent et al., 2018).

So What?

350 FACcTS distributed across seven DLATs were implemented as optional content for newly enrolled students. FACcTS enabled the students who need extra scaffolding to exploit these formative assessment questions to better retain their knowledge and assess their understanding of the topics before they take the summative assessments (Bloom, 1968). Survey responses and comparative analytics of results indicated that students benefited from the FACcTS in three core areas

- First, students who completed FACcTS demonstrated improved summative assessment results, including statistically significant improvement in two DLATs. The analysis further demonstrated that overall engagement of students who completed the FACcTS has shown improvement.

- Second, FACcTS transformed the online learning environment into a more interactive and engaging experience through highly interactive question formats, aligning with Christersson et al.'s (2019) findings on diverse assessment elements' impact on learning. Students identified these functionalities as gamification elements, particularly the star ratings, which created an exciting "game-based" learning experience.
- Third, FACcTS facilitated metacognition by enabling students to pause and reflect on their learning strategies through peer-embedded experiences, allowing them to recognize strengths and weaknesses and adjust their approaches accordingly (Wafubwa & Csíkos, 2022). Students developed sophisticated awareness of knowledge gaps and learning progress, enabling informed decisions about study strategies and summative assessment readiness. The immediate feedback loop boosted student confidence in knowledge retention, exemplifying transformative learning autonomy.

Peer-aligned design recognition, in which student experiences are systematically embedded within assessment questions; feedback-driven learning loops, facilitating iterative learning through timely and targeted feedback; and personalised learning adoption, which fosters the development of self-regulation strategies, constitute key underlying factors contributing to the observed positive impact of FACcTS.

Now What?

Although resource-intensive—requiring a combined 400 hours from students and a module coordinator—the approach has had a positive impact on students' learning experiences in subsequent semesters. Insights from the design and implementation phases provided a practical framework for creating interactive formative assessments and selecting appropriate technologies to embed student experience into module design. Overall, this research demonstrates that co-created assessments offer a scalable, evidence-based model for enhancing large asynchronous modules and advancing student-centred learning initiatives.

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Reimagining Feedback at Scale: Using “Sense Checks” to Model Inclusive Pedagogy in a Large-Class Teacher Education Programme.

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Keywords: Large-class pedagogy; real-time feedback; AfL; inclusive pedagogy; technology-enhanced learning; teacher education

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What?

This presentation focuses on a 10 ECTS postgraduate module within the Graduate Diploma in Inclusive and Special Education (GDISE) at Dublin City University. I taught seven of 21 sessions in this module, all of which incorporated the “Sense Check” approach described below. The module was delivered in a blended format to a large and highly diverse cohort of 115 postgraduate students. All participants were practising educators working across primary, post-primary and special education contexts, bringing significantly varied pedagogical backgrounds, levels of teaching experience, and professional learning needs. This complexity, not only the size of the cohort but the breadth of roles and contextual demands, highlighted the need for regular, embedded feedback and feedforward approaches to monitor understanding and ensure that instruction remained inclusive, appropriately paced, and responsive across my seven sessions.

The pedagogical challenge, aligned with Nind, Curtin and Hall’s (2016) six pedagogical pillars and consistent with challenges identified in the large-class literature around monitoring understanding and sustaining equitable participation at scale (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010; Cuseo, 2007), centred on maintaining meaningful engagement and gathering authentic, real-time feedback in a blended large-class environment. Traditional end-of-module surveys provided only retrospective insights, limiting their usefulness for adaptive teaching during the module.

To address this challenge, I implemented an end-of-session “Sense Check,” modelled on the ‘Exit Ticket’ approach and framed explicitly as an Assessment for Learning (AfL) strategy. Drawing on Black and Wiliam’s (2009) AfL principles and Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick’s (2006) work on formative feedback, the “Sense Check” provided a structured mechanism for students to reflect on their learning while providing me with timely insights to adjust pedagogy. Using Vevox, an audience-response system supported by DCU, students completed five short rating-scale items and two open-ended prompts regarding session content, opportunities to contribute, and the overall learning experience.

Students completed the “Sense Check” in the final five minutes of class, with access open for 48 hours after the session, to support flexibility and accessibility. Participation rates ranged from 75–90%, providing a strong cross-section of the cohort.

So What?

The “Sense Check” established a continuous, low-stakes feedback loop that enhanced engagement, inclusion, and responsiveness. Quantitative data revealed trends in student satisfaction and clarity of instruction, while qualitative feedback offered actionable insights into the learning experience.

Discussing key findings at the start of each subsequent session fostered a transparent feedback dialogue (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006) that students described as validating and inclusive. This process strengthened belonging and co-agency (Trowler, 2010), reinforcing the idea of learning as co-constructed rather than delivered.

For my own professional practice, the “Sense Check” reframed evaluation as an embedded, iterative, and dialogic process (Chalmers & Gardiner, 2015). It informed evidence-based adjustments to pacing, scaffolding, and resources while generating structured data for reflective practice. Importantly, many participants recognised the “Sense Check” as a transferable model of formative assessment and inclusive pedagogy applicable across educational sectors.

The approach is intentionally platform-agnostic, ensuring transferability across modules, disciplines, and technologies. Within this teacher education context, the “Sense Check” also serves a modelling function, demonstrating an inclusive, reflective, and feedback-rich pedagogy that educators could adopt in their diverse teaching environments.

Now What?

Next steps include conducting a longitudinal analysis of “Sense Check” data to identify trends in engagement and satisfaction across cohorts and delivery modes. Such analysis will inform enhancements to session design and provide an evidence base for refining inclusive, feedback-rich practices. Extending the “Sense Check” approach across the wider GDISE programme also has the potential to strengthen programme coherence in learner-responsive pedagogy.

More broadly, this work demonstrates how technology-enabled, inclusive evaluation strategies can meaningfully enhance pedagogy in large-class higher education contexts. Its tool-agnostic and low-resource design makes it highly scalable and adaptable across disciplines, supporting sustainable approaches to large-class teaching.

This initiative aligns with DCU’s commitment to inclusive, evidence-informed pedagogy. It reflects the principles of the UNESCO Education for Sustainable Development Framework (2020), which emphasises participatory, reflective, and learner-centred approaches. Within teacher education specifically, it illustrates how innovations in large-class pedagogy can simultaneously enhance student learning and model the type of inclusive, dialogic, and feedback-driven practices that participants can utilise in their own diverse professional contexts.

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SESSION TWO: TEACHING APPROACHES IN LARGE CLASSES

Co-Teaching for Impact: A Team-Led Approach to AI and Sustainable Innovation

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What?

This reflection details a co-taught final-year undergraduate module titled *Artificial Intelligence & Leading Sustainable Innovation*, offered within final year of the Marketing, Innovation and Technology undergraduate programme. It is a five credit, semester 1 module that is delivered in-person to a cohort of approximately 200 students and is jointly delivered by Prof. Regina Connolly, whose expertise lies in digital transformation and responsible AI leadership, and Dr. Peter Robbins, who specialises in design thinking and innovation management. The module combines lectures with challenge-based learning. Students participate in a live project in partnership with *An Garda Síochána* and *ESB*, developing AI-supported publicity campaigns to promote road safety among their peers. The winning student team receives a €1,000 award and advances to a national competition. The assessment approach includes interactive oral examinations and an end of module 'Dragons' Den' style group presentations ensuring students engage both conceptually and practically with innovation processes (Arvanitakis 2021, Auslander, 2000). The pedagogical challenge centred on how to authentically integrate responsible AI with design thinking in a way that fostered deep, active learning rather than surface engagement. We drew on Nind, Curtin & Hall's (2016) pedagogical pillars by designing the module to respond to 'Pedagogies of Connection' by bridging disciplines (AI ethics and design thinking) and connecting students to real-world stakeholders; and 'Pedagogies of Challenge' by asking students to apply emerging technologies ethically to complex, socially significant problems. We also aimed to move beyond transmissive teaching models to one that would develop the critical, ethical, and collaborative capacities that students will require in their careers (Donovan & Hood, 2021).. To do this, we adopted a co-teaching model, blending our disciplinary expertise through dialogic teaching, real-time debate, and joint facilitation of the live challenge

So what?

The co-teaching approach transformed both the learning environment and our pedagogical understanding. The students were highly engaged and the live challenge created a strong sense of

purpose and authenticity, motivating students to connect AI capabilities with human-centred design to address an important societal issue (Dean et al, 2016). From a pedagogical perspective, the co-teaching model reinforced the importance of social constructivist learning (Vygotsky, 1978) as we modelled the co-construction of knowledge and critical thinking that we hoped to foster in our students. The inclusion of oral assessments aligned with pedagogies of engagement (Nind et al., 2016), encouraging reflection and communication. However, we also learned that a team-led approach requires far greater investment of time and planning than expected. In future iterations, we intend to formalise our reflective practice as co-educators to better align the emphasis of our respective contributions. Ultimately, this experience deepened our own understanding of pedagogies of authenticity (Herrington & Oliver, 2000) and the value of disciplinary collaboration.

Now what?

Our next step is to expand the co-teaching and challenge-based approach to other modules that explore technology and sustainability. We plan to further integrate multi-stakeholder partnerships, thereby extending the model of connected and participatory learning that Nind et al. (2016) advocate. At a broader level, our module raises important questions about how universities can prepare students for leadership in a rapidly transforming digital society. Team-led teaching challenges traditional academic silos and assessment norms, but collaborative, authentic, and dialogic pedagogies may be essential to cultivating graduates who are capable of addressing the complex challenges that digital innovation will bring (Auslander, 2000). It points to the institutional need to value and resource co-teaching as a deliberate pedagogical strategy. For us, as educators, this experience has reaffirmed that innovation in teaching requires experimentation, partnership, and reflection. Our aim moving forward is to continue refining this co-teaching model as an example of responsible, collaborative learning in action.

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Digital transformation for active, inclusive and sustainable learning in a large engineering module

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What?

Engineering Mechanics: Dynamics (MEC1000) is a 5-credit Spring-semester module with over 170 second-year students. The class is highly mathematical and has historically experienced low engagement. The redesign was implemented in January 2025 and delivered by the module coordinator together with one teaching assistant who supported weekly tutorials. The module was therefore restructured to create a more inclusive and sustainable learning environment through a targeted digital transformation:

- A clear Loop structure was introduced with dedicated hubs for Learning, Problem-Solving, Online Labs, and External Resources to improve navigation and reduce cognitive load.
- Short blended mini-lectures were recorded to demonstrate worked examples, while a new Problem-Solving Hub on the Loop page enabled students to practise independently and at their own pace. Also, the WileyPLUS multimedia learning hub, which includes interactive solved examples, tutorials, and virtual labs, was integrated into the Loop page to support inclusive and active learning.
- To address limited laboratory capacity, two-thirds of the physical labs were replaced by interactive online simulations integrated with an AI-powered quiz generator developed in collaboration with the DCU Teaching Enhancement Unit (TEU).
- Rubric-based automated grading was implemented for lab report writing to enhance fairness, feedback and transparency.

So What?

The redesign produced tangible improvements in learning and engagement outcomes.

- Average attendance rose from 40% to 65%, median marks increased by 24% (from 51 to 63.3), and pass rates reached 86%, the highest in more than a decade.
- Students described the module as “very well organised” and “easy to follow” in a survey, reflecting the positive impact of allowing learners in large-scale classes to progress at their own pace and according to their individual needs (Straits, 2007).

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- Beyond performance metrics, the digital redesign broadened inclusivity by diversifying assessments and offering multiple pathways for participation, a core principle of universal design and active engagement, often overlooked in large-scale modules (Rose et al., 2014; Laria, 2008).
- Students could engage with material asynchronously, review worked examples repeatedly, and complete equivalent online labs regardless of physical access or timetable constraints, significantly improving their virtual learning experience (O'Connor, 2021).
- These practices embody the principles of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), as recognised through my DCU-ESD badge, by promoting systems thinking, self-regulation and collaboration, while modelling sustainability through efficient digital resource use and reduced physical dependency (Ferguson, 2021).

Now What?

Building on these results, future iterations will:

- Integrate learning-analytics dashboards to monitor engagement patterns and refine digital inclusivity further.
- Disseminate the Loop structure, AI-quiz templates, and automated-rubric system as open educational resources within the PHELC community, supporting colleagues teaching large STEM cohorts.
- Inform the redesign of other foundational engineering modules, contributing to DCU's Teaching and Learning Strategy and aligning with the UNESCO ESD 2030 framework by demonstrating how technology-enabled pedagogy can deliver active, equitable, and sustainable learning at scale.

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Using Self-Study to Enhance the Teaching of Self-Study with Pre-Service Teachers

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What?

In this presentation, I will explore my experience of using self-study methodology to enhance my teaching of self-study to final year undergraduate students in a teacher education programme.

Despite the burgeoning popularity of self-study research amongst teacher educators, there is a dearth of research conducted on the teaching and learning of self-study, and it has been embraced in a very limited capacity by pre-service teachers (Loughran, 2018; Ritter, 2017).

The module had a student cohort of approximately 400 students, and as module coordinator, I taught weekly plenaries with the whole group and led a team of 44 dissertation tutors who met the students in small seminar groups six times in the semester.

My research question focused on: How can I enhance my teaching of self-study in this teaching context?

This included three sub-questions:

- How can I make learning about self-study engaging?
- How can I make doing self-study accessible to all students?
- How can I make the completion of a self-study dissertation less vulnerable to plagiarism/AI?

So What?

Given that self-study is “lived rather than learned” (Diacopoulos et al., 2022, p.175), I embarked on a self-study that would mirror the journey asked of my students. Therefore, in this study, I used the same data collection tools that I hoped that the students would use in their self-studies.

The data encouraged me to develop several formative tasks and guide documents within the lecturing space so as to assist the students with the process of self-study while also making the learning outcomes for the lecture clearer to me. This allowed for more active learning (Mantai & Huber, 2021) and deeper thinking (Hornsby & Osman, 2014) by students in the large lecture hall. I advised the tutor group to deepen the work begun in the lecture using the guide documents as a link between the two learning spaces. I also

began to create worked examples of reflective logs based on student queries and I began to investigate AI tools that assisted with the research process.

The reflective data also urged me to consider using interactive quizzes and on-line interactive questioning forums within the lecture hall to enhance engagement (Mulryan- Kyne, 2010). I also discovered that the critical friend model that I had required of students was very challenging. This led me to re-think how it was presented and conducted, resulting in the development of a guide document based on my experiences. Ultimately, my self-study highlighted the importance of explicit modelling and opportunities for students to engage in guided practice in both the lecture hall and small group seminars before attempting independent work.

Now What?

This self-study made me very aware of the assumptions that I held about teaching and learning research methods. It is very important to use reflective data to 'stand in and outside' of oneself (Brookfield, 2017, p.17) in order to understand the student experience. It highlights the need to focus on the learning process in order to achieve a more transformative learning space that is active, interactive and valued by students. As a self-study, this paper is highly contextual but is intended to provide useful insights into the teaching and learning of self-study in higher education contexts.

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SESSION THREE: LEARNING AND ENGAGEMENT IN LARGE CLASSES

Transforming Business Education: The Impact of the LIFE Module at Dublin City University

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This abstract summarises a forthcoming book chapter:

Elliott, D., Faherty, C., Real, C., & Lyons, R. (2025). The Impact of the LIFE Module at Dublin City University. In N. O'Regan & G. Feiger (Eds.), *Reconnecting Business Schools with Business*. Taylor & Francis.

What?

This presentation is based on an introductory business module which is delivered to all DCU Business School first-year students (c800) across all eleven undergraduate business degree programmes. The Learning Innovation for Enterprise (LIFE) module has been in place since 2019 and draws on best practices from academic research, industry collaboration, and international frameworks. It is a ten-credit, year-long module delivered in-person to approximately 270 students in each lecture (i.e., involves triple delivery), and is currently co-taught by Dr. Catherine Faherty and Dr. Colette Real from the Enterprise and Innovation Group within DCU Business School.

The challenge was to create a module which embodies the principles of enterprise education, which, as described by Jones and Iredale (2010) should include:

- **Active learning pedagogy:** Employing experiential, challenge-based learning where students “learn by doing.”
- **Relevant knowledge:** Equipping students with the skills to function effectively as citizens, employees, or entrepreneurs in a flexible market economy.
- **Skill development:** Enhancing personal skills, behaviours, and attributes applicable in various contexts.
- **Fostering enterprising individuals:** Encouraging students to think and act enterprisingly across diverse settings, including their communities, workplaces, and as entrepreneurs.
- **Lifelong learning:** Promoting the application of enterprising skills and behaviours throughout life.

An additional challenge was to integrate the competencies and recommendations of the EU EntreComp Framework into the curriculum design. The EntreComp Framework emphasises the development of entrepreneurial mindsets and the ability to create, implement, and adapt innovative solutions.

Furthermore, the ongoing challenge is to deliver this module in the context of a large class size which can inhibit active student engagement (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010) and can be particularly difficult for first-year students undergoing the transition from school to university (Cuseo, 2007). Our aim, following the principles of universal design for learning, is to provide a variety of options for content representation and student engagement and expression in order to meet the needs of the diverse variety of students in the classroom across a range of business programmes (e.g., accounting, marketing, aviation, digital, and general business students).

For the purposes of this abstract and resulting presentation, the incorporation of challenge-based learning into the module is focused upon specifically.

So What?

The pedagogical approach for the LIFE module is firmly grounded in Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) (Membrillo-Hernández et al., 2019), a methodology that emphasises real-world problem-solving. Industry engagement and collaboration with business partners is a core element of our approach. Faculty members, alongside business and industry leaders, work closely to identify real-world challenges that guide students in deepening their knowledge and applying it in active, meaningful, relevant, and impactful ways.

Spanning two semesters, the LIFE module is structured into four distinct yet interconnected elements, each designed to provide students with experiential learning opportunities that align with contemporary business challenges. This foundational module fosters entrepreneurial thinking and innovation by immersing students in the real-world dynamics of enterprise across four key contexts: start-ups, corporate enterprise, family business, and social enterprise.

The first section introduces students to **entrepreneurship** and business start-ups, with a series of lectures and entrepreneur guest speakers. Students complete a psychometric self-assessment of their own entrepreneurship competencies and are tasked with a series of challenges to apply and practice these competencies and behaviors in their own lives. This section culminates with students creating their own entrepreneurial reflective learning portfolio using the DCU Loop Reflect system (Mahara software), a learner-centered personal learning environment. This portfolio also allows students to compete for the Dr. Seamus McDermot Liffey Trust Entrepreneurial Scholarship worth €9000 over the course of their DCU programme.

The second element shifts the focus to **intrapreneurship** and innovative thinking within established organisations. Students participate in a corporate innovation challenge using design-thinking techniques to develop creative solutions to a real-world challenge posed by a sponsoring organisation, which in recent years has been the Irish company Applegreen, a leading roadside hospitality retailer. In response to a real challenge set by the company, students work in groups, conduct market research by visiting Applegreen

stores, and develop proposals and prototypes for innovations aligned with the strategic priorities outlined during the company's guest lecture. The most innovative solution is presented to Applegreen management by the student group, and each member receives a commemorative award from the company.

The third section explores the unique dynamics of **family businesses**. Students engage with family business leaders through a 'live case study series', gaining insights into the challenges and strategies of managing multi-generational family enterprises. Assignments in this section are deeply rooted in real-world application: students analyse and document the practices of family innovators in their communities, producing mini-case video documentaries that showcase their findings and learnings.

The final section focuses on **social enterprise**, encouraging students to address societal challenges through innovation. Central to this element is our 'DCU Hack4Change', a social innovation hackathon series where students collaborate to develop impactful solutions to social challenges and address sustainable development goals. Guided by talks and coaching from Ireland's leading social entrepreneurs, students engage in intensive ideation and problem-solving. In recent years this section has been sponsored by Deloitte Ireland, who add the dimension of responsible business, corporate social responsibility, and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) frameworks of large organisations. The final assessment for this module involves the creation of a reflective learning portfolio on the nature of social innovation and on the student's Hackathon experience, again using the DCU Loop Reflect system (Mahara software).

Each lecturer delivers two sections of the module, with the final hackathon event co-delivered by both. Workload involves delivering traditional lectures but also extensive industry engagement in relation to guest lectures, co-designed challenge-based learning initiatives, student mentoring, and sponsorship, prizes, and awards. Grading is supported by a team of teaching assistants and with the use of pre-defined detailed grading rubrics developed in conjunction with the Teaching Enhancement Unit in DCU, which ensure consistency and efficiencies in the grading process, along with providing rich individualised feedback to students.

Now What?

The LIFE module is a compelling example of how innovative pedagogy can transform the student experience and deliver tangible impacts. By integrating challenge-based learning and real-world engagement, the module equips students with both the knowledge and the skills to thrive in an increasingly complex and dynamic business environment.

Furthermore, enterprise education is not solely related to business (Jones & Iredale, 2010). The EU Entrecomp policy highlights that entrepreneurship skills apply to all spheres of life and can create financial, cultural, or social value. In this respect, elements of the design of the LIFE module, in particular the approach to challenge-based learning for large student cohorts firmly situated in business and the community, can be relevant across all university disciplines and programmes.

Where do we go from here? Challenge-based learning will remain at the heart of our student experience. This requires ongoing strong engagement with industry and community enterprises, to co-design and refresh

our curriculum, to sponsor real world challenges, and to mentor students and share their time in multiple ways. For students, learning innovation for enterprise is equally relevant to both career management and community involvement, and a key competency for life-long learning, work, and civic engagement.

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Balancing Efficiency and Effectiveness: Learning in Large Class Electronics Laboratories

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What?

Engineering laboratories are grounded in constructivist pedagogy; there is value in the experience of participating; this scaffolds learning and teaches unique skills (Feisel & Rosa, 2005). The massification of higher education means we are welcoming more diverse students (Hornsby & Osman, 2014), ultimately producing engineers who better reflect the societies they design for. Maintaining pedagogically valuable laboratory experiences can be challenging with large cohorts. We discuss our approach for two separate laboratory curricula within Electronic Engineering for undergraduate students at DCU. Practicals for each module are facilitated by one academic (the module convenor), one technical officer, and three/four postgraduate demonstrators (usually Masters students).

- EEG1004: Introduction to Electronics. 5 ECTS credits, year-long, \approx 250 first year students (all engineering disciplines).
- EEN1022: Digital & Analogue Electronics. 5 ECTS credits, semester 1, \approx 200 second year students (Electronic and Computer Engineering, Mechatronic Engineering, and Physics).

We focus on *pedagogy as planned* in the design of sessions and *pedagogy as enacted/experienced* (Nind et al., 2016) in the delivery.

So What?

With large classes, efficient laboratory design is critical. Detailed instructions/manuals provided in advance, highlight common mistakes and guide fault-finding, empowering students to help themselves. EEG1004 incorporates automatically graded “pre-laboratory” assessments; based on laboratory instructions so students arrive prepared (Rollnick et al., 2001) these are ‘summative assessments with a formative flavour’ (Broadbent et al., 2018) providing timely and individualised feedback.

It is difficult to know students individually in large classes, so pedagogical design addresses collective patterns of understanding, scaffolding students in developing mastery (Woollacott et al., 2014). Laboratories also offer active learning experiences which can be otherwise challenging to deliver in large cohorts (Felder, 1997), (Hornsby & Osman, 2014).

Planning for failure is built into activity design; learning from mistakes is valuable (Edmunds & Leggett, 2024), but only if students can understand the cause and take this learning forwards (Molloy et al., 2020). This is balanced with keeping students motivated while waiting for help in large classes. Sessions are designed to minimize destructive or frustrating failure; circuits may not fully work, but will partially work, allowing students to locate errors more easily.

Circuit construction requires developing skills with unfamiliar technologies and processes. Scaffolding novices to develop competency starts with structured work to build familiarity, gradually increasing difficulty and complexity as students gain independence. Experts model the skills, reducing cognitive load on students (Atkinson et al., 2000). EEN1022 begins with a step-by-step cohort construction of the first circuit to increase confidence, ensuring early success for everyone. EEG1004 starts with “what you see is what you get” images of circuits. Later, circuit schematic diagrams are introduced, increasing in complexity throughout the module as students develop interpretation skills.

The physical laboratory space is an invaluable pedagogical tool for developing identity and community among engineers (Winberg & Winberg, 2021). Students experience excitement and achievement when their constructed circuits work. Laboratories develop student feedback literacy; providing space to benchmark work and observe peer progress.

Now What?

Large group laboratories require compromise between the efficiency of rigidly structured procedural construction, and the development of higher-level skills such as independent investigation and creation (key to Bloom’s taxonomy and engineering accreditation). Both modules achieve this compromise by providing more structure initially and becoming more open-ended later. Laboratories are important for developing disciplinary specific skills (construction and fault-finding) and act as a learning forum. Students report enjoying laboratories; therefore, further investigation into pedagogy as experienced by our students is warranted as we continue developing curricula.

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Supporting Diverse Learners in Large First-Year Classes through Adaptive Digital Tools: Integrating McGraw Hill Connect in Anatomy and Physiology

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What?

Teaching Anatomy and Physiology to large first-year cohorts presents growing pedagogical challenges. This 5-credit, semester-long module now enrolls ~400 students from Nursing, Health & Society, and Biomedical Engineering—a 25% increase over three years. This growth has coincided with a clear performance divide: a strong high and middle band alongside an emerging lower band struggling to progress, reflected in rising repeat rates. Contributing factors include cohort scale and highly varied academic backgrounds, with increasing numbers of students entering with limited prior exposure to biology or chemistry, making timely, individualised feedback difficult using traditional approaches.

These challenges align with the pedagogical pillars of teaching, learning, assessment, and values described by Nind, Curtin, and Hall (2016). This initiative responds to these pillars as follows:

- **Teaching:** Uses adaptive SmartBook tools to support active, self-directed learning and regular engagement.
- **Learning:** Enables students to work at their own pace with personalised feedback, supporting understanding—particularly for lower-performing students.
- **Assessment:** Introduces 20% continuous assessment (CA) via SmartBook quizzes, reducing reliance on single high-stakes exams.
- **Values:** Embeds UDL principles to promote inclusivity and accessibility (Sanger, 2020).

To operationalise these goals, adaptive learning approaches—digital systems that personalise learning pathways based on student performance—were adopted due to their documented impact on engagement and outcomes in large, diverse cohorts (Martin et al., 2020). Implementation was supported by McGraw Hill's Learning Matters grant, which provided funding and technical support for adopting the Connect platform.

SmartBook delivers topic readings and short adaptive MCQ quizzes that adjust to each student's responses,

generating personalised follow-up content and feedback. Materials are available in multiple formats (text, visuals, audio, video) to support accessibility and diverse learning preferences. The assessment structure has been revised from 100% exam to an 80% exam / 20% CA model using quizzes across eight topics. Starting Semester 2 (January 2025).

So What?

Although implementation is upcoming, the initiative is expected to:

1. **Increase engagement and self-directed learning** through adaptive, self-paced materials and immediate feedback.
2. **Improve progression among weaker-performing students** via personalised pathways and earlier identification of difficulties.
3. **Diversify assessment and feedback** through regular CA and automated, personalised feedback.

By offering multimodal resources and personalised learning pathways, the approach supports inclusive, responsive learning aligned with UDL and the pedagogical pillars of diversity, massification, and inclusivity (Nind et al., 2016; Sanger, 2020). Automated adaptive feedback also reflects Nicol's (2010) principles of self-regulated learning by providing timely, personalised guidance that promotes autonomy without increasing staff workload. This is particularly valuable in large-class contexts challenges where traditional feedback structures are strained (Hornsby & Osman, 2014; Mulryan-Kyne, 2010).

Now What?

Outcomes will be evaluated through student feedback, engagement analytics, and exam performance. Key challenges include sustaining engagement and securing long-term funding, though embedding the platform within CA should mitigate this. The approach is transferable to other disciplines and large-cohort modules by showing how adaptive learning, UDL principles, and analytics can support diverse learners. Looking ahead, AI may be used to develop an in-house platform based on existing module resources to deliver scalable, personalised learning support.

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Session Three: Learning and Engagement in Large Classes: Supporting Diverse Learners in Large First-Year Classes through Adaptive Digital Tools: Integrating McGraw Hill Connect in Anatomy and Physiology

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